

RASHID 2 MISSION: UAE'S SECOND MISSION TO THE MOON SURFACE. H. Almatroushi¹, H. Almarzouqi¹, A. Sharaf¹, S. Els¹, H. AlAhmed², and S. AlMulla¹, ¹Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC), Dubai, UAE, ²Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre Lab, University of Dubai, Dubai, UAE.

Introduction: The Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM) program, initiated by the United Arab Emirates (UAE), reflects the nation's growing commitment to space exploration and technological advancement. Motivated by Mars2117 vision to establish a human settlement on Mars by the year 2117, the ELM program strengthens the UAE's position in the global space community as it aims at developing and landing a series of small rovers to different sites on the lunar surface to expand our knowledge of the lunar environment and test developed technologies on it.

The first step towards achieving this goal was the successful launch of the first Emirates Lunar Mission, Rashid 1, marking the UAE's first venture onto the Moon. Even though Rashid 1 landing was not successful in 2023, the ambition continues with Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC) working on two follow-up missions: Rashid 2 and Rashid 3.

This paper will focus on the development of Rashid 2 mission, its science objectives, and payloads.

Rashid 2 Development: Rashid 2 builds upon the technological advancements and lessons learned from Rashid 1. It is considered almost an exact replica of the Rashid 1 rover and is intended to land at a mid-latitude site on the Moon, offering new opportunities for exploration and science. The mission will carry the same payloads as its predecessor, with new experimental materials mounted on its wheels. The payloads are designed to study the Moon's surface in high resolution, analyze its plasma environment, investigate the composition of the lunar regolith, and understand its thermal properties.

Rashid 2 Objectives: The primary objective of Rashid 2 mission is to prepare and demonstrate the UAE's national capability in developing and operating a mobile robot on another celestial body. Its secondary objective focuses on obtaining scientific data that will be relevant and useful for designing future lunar missions, as well as fundamental research. The main scientific objectives are:

- Study the geological and thermal aspects of the lunar surface in different locations.
- Study and map the electrical charge process and the formation of the electron sheath on the surface throughout the lunar day.
- Perform science and engineering experiments related to materials, mobility, and terramechanics.

Rashid 2 Payloads: Rashid 2 will carry a set of specialized payloads designed to address its scientific objectives. The payloads include the following (see Figure 1):

- Main Camera (CAM-1)

- Secondary Camera (CAM-2)
- Microscopic Imager (CAM-M)
- Thermal Imager (CAM-T)
- Langmuir Probe System (LNG)
- Material Adhesion/Abrasion Detection Experiments (MAD)

Figure 1: Rashid 2 Rover and Payloads

The lightweighted instruments selected for this mission were chosen carefully to meet the mission objectives and maximize the scientific return of Rashid 2 mission while operating on the lunar surface. The data returned from these instruments will aid in studying the Moon's geography and environment and provide insights to its present state and history.

Main Camera (CAM-1). The main optical camera (CAM-1) will provide high-resolution colored images in full HD for the surface of the moon. It is mounted on top of the rover's mast to provide panoramic visibility of the rover surroundings to support navigation, operations, and science.

Secondary Camera (CAM-2). The secondary camera (CAM-2) has the same specifications as the main camera (CAM-1). It is mounted on the rear of the rover to provide visibility for reverse drive operations. It will deliver high-resolution colored images of the lunar surface and the drive tracks. Such data will be important to design the mobility systems of future rovers.

Microscopic Imager (CAM-M). The microscopic imager will obtain the highest resolution image from the lunar surface and provide an unprecedented view of the undisturbed topmost layer of the lunar regolith. This will help in performing petrographic studies of lunar rocks and soil.

Thermal Imager (CAM-T). The thermal imager (CAM-T) will provide data of the thermal behaviour of the lunar surface structure. Thermal surface imagery from CAM-T will provide thermal properties of rocks, boulders, ridges, etc, hence, provide to some extent insight into their interior composition and structure.

Langmuir Probe System (LNG). Langmuir probes will study the plasma around the Moon. It will measure the density of the lunar electron sheath within the first meter above the surface. The data will help in understanding how charged particles interact with the lunar surface.

Material Adhesion / Abrasion Detection Experiments (MAD). Material Adhesion / Abrasion Detection (MAD) Experiment is intended to mount different material samples on the wheels of the rover to test their interaction with the lunar regolith (or other experimenting aspects of the lunar regolith interaction). The MAD experimental setup makes use of the continuous surfaces between the grousers of the rover wheels. While driving, the wheels will bring those samples into repetitive contact with the lunar surface regolith. The interaction of this frequent exposure of the samples to the lunar surface material will then be observable by means of imaging with the mast mounted camera CAM-1.

Conclusion: Rashid 2 marks a crucial step forward in the UAE's space exploration program. Through its focused science objectives and advanced payloads, Rashid 2 will deepen our understanding of the Moon's surface and environment, contributing valuable data for future lunar missions. The mission's mid-latitude landing site and continuation of the Rashid 1 payloads ensure that critical data will be collected across different lunar regions. Rashid 2 will lay the groundwork for Rashid 3, which will push the boundaries of lunar exploration further by incorporating more advanced technologies. These missions collectively reflect the UAE's commitment to space exploration and its role in advancing global scientific knowledge.